

A reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification for broad coverage detection of Asian and African Zika virus lineages

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Table S3. Time threshold of positivity for RT-LAMP assays of serially diluted ZIKV RNA.

	Time Threshold (Tt-value, min)			
ZIKV RNA copy number	1000	100	10	1
Replicates				
1	28.24	49.00	35.24	-
2	25.24	30.42	42.42	-
3	26.42	29.36	62.06	39.06
4	27.18	39.30	36.30	-